

Monothelitism

also known as “monotheletism”

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Byzantine, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy

Monothelitism, or monotheletism was a theological teaching, according to which Jesus Christ had only one will, being thus contrary to dyothelitism, the Christological formula that held that Jesus Christ had two wills, a divine and a human. Monothelitism emerged as a result of the Christological controversies that were related to the monophysitism of Eutyches of Constantinople, and the miaphysitist formula of the followers of St. Cyril of Alexandria. During the 5th century there was turmoil in some regions of the Byzantine Empire due to the debates over the nature of Jesus Christ. Although the official doctrine of the Church determined that Christ is indeed the son of God, His exact nature nevertheless remained open to speculation. During the debates over Arianism, the first Council of Nicaea in 325 had declared as heretical the idea that Jesus Christ is not fully divine, while it also made clear that Jesus is God, the Son of God who became human. However, in arguing that Jesus is both God and man, a conflict emerged relating to the way that the human and divine natures actually exist within the person of Christ. At the Council of Chalcedon, in 451, the Eastern Orthodox Church defined that Jesus Christ had two distinct natures, a divine and a human; yet they come together within His one hypostasis. This means that Jesus Christ is known as both fully human and fully Divine, one in being with the Father. This doctrinal formula was opposed by the Monophysites, who held that Christ possessed only one nature. They held that the human and divine natures of Jesus Christ were fused into one new single nature. As described by Eutyches, Jesus' human nature was dissolved like a drop of honey in the sea, so His nature is only the divine one. These debates led the Chalcedonians to accuse the non-Chalcedonians of teaching Christ's humanity to be of a different kind from our own; while the non-Chalcedonians accused the Chalcedonians of following a form of Nestorianism, the belief, that is, that Jesus Christ was two distinct subsistences. The doctrinal turmoil was dangerous for the Byzantine Empire, which was under constant threat, especially as many of the areas most likely to be lost to the Empire were the regions that were in favor of Monophysites, who considered the hierarchy at Constantinople to be heretics. In these provinces, the non-Chalcedonians were far more numerous than the Chalcedonians. Under these circumstances, the Monothelite formula emerged as a compromise position. The Byzantine emperor Heraclius (610-641) tried to promote monothelitism as a unifying doctrine, that would reconcile and eventually unite the divided Christian factions within the Empire. His goal was to win over the non-Chalcedonians, since they already believed that Jesus Christ has a single nature, therefore He holds a single will. For this reason, Patriarch Sergius I of Constantinople (610-638) came up with a christological formula, which the Emperor Heraclius released as an edict in 638. The edict proclaimed that Christ has two natures but a single will. But both the Emperor and the Patriarch had not counted on the popes at Rome. Pope Severinus condemned Heraclius's edict, while his successor, Pope John IV (640-642), also rejected the doctrine completely, leading to a major schism between the eastern and western Church. The schism remained for the next few years. Meanwhile in Africa, a monk, Maximus the Confessor, carried on a furious campaign against Monothelitism, and in 646, he convinced the African councils to draw up a manifesto against the doctrine, which they forwarded to the new pope, Theodore I (642-649), who, in turn, wrote to Patriarch Paul II of Constantinople to outline the heretical nature of Monothelitism. Monothelitism was finally condemned at the Council of Constantinople (Sixth Ecumenical Council) took place from 680 to 681. Participants included the Pope's representatives, representatives from the Patriarchs of Alexandria and Jerusalem, while the Patriarchs of Constantinople and Antioch were present in person. It condemned the Monothelite doctrine as one that diminished the fullness of Christ's humanity and asserted Dyothelitism to

be the true doctrine, with Christ possessing two natural wills and two natural energies, without division, alteration, separation or confusion.

Date Range: 456 CE - 681 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire (395-632)

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Middle East

Byzantine Empire (395-632)

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Acta Conciliorum Oecumenicorum, ser. 2, II.1-2. ed. R. Riedinger (Berlin 1990 and 1992).
- Source 2: Cyril Hovorun, (2008), Will, Action and Freedom: Christological Controversies in the Seventh Century. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Source 3: John Meyendorff, (1989), Imperial unity and Christian divisions: The Church 450-680 A.D. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press.
- Source 1: George C. Berthold (1985), Maximus Confessor: Selected Writings, Paulist Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oca.org/orthodoxy/the-orthodox-faith/church-history/seventh-century/monoenergism-monotheism>
- Source 1 Description: Monoenergism / Monothelism
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Monothelite>
- Source 2 Description: Monothelite Christianity
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/10502a.htm>
- Source 3 Description: Monothelism and Monothelites
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v8w_xGG76qY
- Source 1 Description: The Monothelism Versus Dyothelism Debate
- Source 2 URL: <https://wtctheology.org.uk/theomisc/tag/monothelism/>
- Source 2 Description: monothelism

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/laprimauteetlinf00bg/page/n3/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: La primaute et l'infaillibilite des souverains pontifes : lecons d'histoire donnees a l'Universite Laval by Bégin, Louis-Nazaire, 1840-1925

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The religious groups in contact during the period under investigation were the Chalcedonians and the non-Chalcedonians. It was unclear whether the Chalcedonians should believe in Christ's human and divine energy and/or will as well as His human and divine nature because previous Ecumenical Councils had made no ruling on that subject. A ruling for the new doctrine would provide common ground for the non-Chalcedonians and the Chalcedonians to come together, as the non-Chalcedonians could agree that Jesus has two natures if He has only one will, and some Chalcedonians could agree that Jesus has one will if He has two natures.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Byzantine emperor Heraclius, in his effort to unite all of the various theological factions within the empire under a somewhat compromising christological formula, decided to use

Monoenergism as a political weapon to reconcile the Non-Chalcedonian Churches of his Empire. With the successful conclusion to the Persian War, the Emperor was free to devote more time in promoting his compromise, which was now more urgent because of the administration of the recovered Monophysite provinces of Syria and Egypt. He therefore released with Patriarch Sergius the "Ecthesis", in 638, an edict that forbade all mention of Christ possessing one or two energies and proclaimed that Christ has two natures but a single will. This did not deny Christ human volition, but insisted that this volition could never be in opposition to the divine will; but the opponents of one will misinterpreted the doctrine as denying Christ any human volition whatsoever. Heraclius' young grandson Constans II (641-668) succeeded him. This latter was only 17 and was indifferent to the religious debates of the Church. However, he was concerned about the effect that the debate had to the Empire. He therefore issued an imperial edict, called the "Type", according to which it was illegal to discuss in any manner Christ possessing either one or two wills or one or two energies. He declared that the whole controversy was to be forgotten. However, he would soon discover that the controversy would not die down. After Constans's death in 668, the throne passed to his son Constantine IV. Pope Vitalian (657-672), who had hosted the visit of Constans II to Rome in 663, almost immediately declared himself for the doctrine of the two wills of Christ. In response, Patriarch Theodore I of Constantinople and Macarius, Patriarch of Antioch, both pressed Constantine to take some measures against the pope. Constantine, however, decided to let the Monothelite question be decided entirely by a church council.

- ↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
 - No
- ↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
 - No
- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the exact number of the partisans of Monothelism is unknown, in Egypt some 30,000 Greeks of Chalcedonian persuasion were ranged against some five million Coptic non-Chalcedonians. Meanwhile, Syria and Mesopotamia were divided between Nestorianism and Jacobitism, while the religion of Armenia was wholly Non-Chalcedonian.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Tombs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Altars:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
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Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– No

In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes

- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes

- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE
Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: A kind of punishment was religious condemnation and excommunication. Both Pope Severinus and his successor, Pope John IV condemned the Emperor Heraclius and his monothelitic policy. Pope Theodore I excommunicated the Patriarch of Constantinople, Paul I, who was a devoted Monothelite. Furthermore, the Lateran Council of 649 condemned Heraclius' edict, as well as the edict issued by Emperor Constans II. After the Council, Pope Martin wrote to Constans to inform him of its conclusions and to require him to condemn the Monothelite doctrine.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Maximus the Confessor, a fierce opponent of Monothelitism, was sent to exile after his trial as a heretic in 658 to Lazica (or Colchis) region of modern-day Georgia and was cast in the fortress of Schemarum, perhaps Muris-Tsikhe near the modern town of Tsageri

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Maximus the Confessor, a fierce opponent of Monothelitism, was tortured having his tongue cut out, so he could no longer speak his rebellion, and his right hand cut off, so that he could no longer write letters. Moreover, Theodore I Calliopas, the exarch of Ravenna, seized Pope Martin and abducted him to Constantinople, where he was imprisoned and tortured before he was condemned for breaking the imperial commands and banished before he died from his treatment at the hands of the Emperor.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 330 CE - 1453 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monothelitism, Allen, Pauline, and Bronwen Neil. *The Oxford Handbook of Maximus the Confessor*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015.

Reference: Monothelitism, Blowers, Paul. *Maximus the Confessor: Jesus Christ and the Transfiguration of the World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Reference: Monothelitism, Radosavljević, Artemije . *Why Did God Become Man? the Unconditionality of the Divine Incarnation. Deification as the End and Fulfillment of Salvation According to St. Maximos the Confessor*. Athens, 1975.

Reference: Monothelitism, Bathrellos, Demetrios. *The Byzantine Christ: Person, Nature, and Will in the Christology of Saint Maximus the Confessor*. Oxford-New York: Oxford University Press, 2004.

Reference: Monothelitism, Hovorun, Cyril. *Will, Action and Freedom: Christological Controversies in the Seventh Century*. Leiden: Brill, 2008.

Reference: Monothelitism, Meyendorff, John. *Imperial Unity and Christian Divisions: The Church 450–680 A.D. The Church in History. Vol. 2..* Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 1989.

Reference: Monothelitism, Bevan, George , and Patrick T. R. Gray. "The Trial of Eutyches: A New Interpretation". *Byzantinische Zeitschrift* 101 (2009): 617–57. <https://doi.org/10.1515/byzs.2008.016>.

Reference: Monothelitism, Cohen , Samuel. "Eutychianorum Furor! Heresiological Comparison and the Invention of Eutychians in Leo I's Christological Polemic". *Entangled Religions* 11, no. 4 (2020): 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.46586/er.11.2020.9434>.

Reference: Monothelitism, Boulnois, Marie-Odile. *Le Paradoxe Trinitaire Chez Cyrille D'alexandrie: Herméneutique, analyses Philosophiques Et Argumentation Théologique..* Collection Des Études Augustiniennes, Série Antiquité 143. Paris: Institute d'études augustiennes, 1994.

Reference: Monothelitism, Allen, Pauline. *Sophronius of Jerusalem and Seventh Century Heresy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Monothelitism, Brock, Sebastian. "Two Sets of Monothelite Questions to the Maximianists". *Orientalia Lovaniensia Periodica* 17 (1986): 119–40.

Reference: Monothelitism, Conterno, Maria. "Three Unpublished Texts on Christ's Unique Will and Operation from the Syriac Florilegium in the Ms. London, British Library, Add. 14535". *Millennium: Yearbook on the Culture and History of the First Millennium C.E.* 10 (2013): 115-44.

Reference: Monothelitism, Hovorun, Cyril . "Controversy on Energies and Wills in Christ: Between Politics and Theology". *Studia Patristica* 48 (2010): 217-20.

Reference: Monothelitism, Clarke, Kevin . "Preserving the Whole Theological System: Maximus the Confessor's Dyothelitism as a Bulwark for Trinitarian Theology, Christology, and Soteriology". *Vox Patrum* 37 (2017): 479-500.